

HEALTHY MEANS OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND SPORTS

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Abstract: *Correlation of physical development, body structure, physical and functional readiness indicators is defined to determine effective means of health improvement. Such an approach, i.e., identification of scientifically based exercises for physical training of students, allows effective planning of health-prevention work, selection of tools in accordance with the goal of accelerating the health process.*

Key words: *fitness, students, exercise, muscle, teaching, pedagogical goal, educational method.*

INTRODUCTION

The success of training depends on the correct determination of its goals and content, as well as the means of achieving these goals, that is, teaching methods. Teaching methods mean a certain orderly, purposeful system of relations between the teacher and the student, which ensures the realization of the pedagogical goals of training improvement. As a result of experimental research, effective methods of valeo-logical education of students (game, competition, strictly regulated exercises and methods of verbal influence) have been determined.

How to play: The method of organizing movement activities in the form of mobile, sports national games is widely used in the process of physical education and has a number of advantages over other methods. The essence of this method is that movement activities are organized based on the content, conditions and rules of the game. Characteristic features of the game method:

a) the activities of the participants are carried out against the background of high morale;

b) complex relationships arise between those involved in the game process.

These features increase students' interest in movement activities, relieve mental fatigue that occurs during the performance of exercises of the same nature; helps to improve mastered movements and master the skill of using them.

Competition method: The method of organizing exercises in the form of a competition. The essence of the competition as a method of education is that it cultivates in students the spirit of friendly, healthy competition, striving to be equal to the strong. Especially the rating system helps with this. The competition method develops interest in physical training.

Strictly regulated exercise method: Strict regulation of exercises is the main methodological direction of the process of conducting experiments in physical fitness classes. The use of methods in this direction helps to develop physical development, strength capabilities that have a positive effect on the structure of the body: it improves the work of the cardiovascular system by running and walking.

METHOD AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Effective means of improving health

Physical exercises have a good effect on the student's respiratory organs and mental state. If the muscles are not regularly activated, the human central nervous system will be deprived of positive charges. Decreased vital tone, depression is accompanied by reactions of anger and lack of self-control. Physical exercises have a positive effect not only on the physical, but also on the mental state of the student, which, in turn, increases the effectiveness of the educational and health process. The receptive period of the development of the human body ends at the student age. During this period, young students will have great opportunities to study, learn, and engage in social and political activities. It is for this reason that physical education and sports are an important tool for strengthening health, which is a natural and

biological basis for raising a perfect person, directly helps to study, engage in science, and acquire a profession.

Physical exercises cause various shifts that have a positive effect on the functioning of human organs and systems. Muscle contractions are the basis of physical exercises, muscles make up 3-4 parts of human weight. The energy of muscle contraction is generated due to the increased flow of oxygen and various nutrients to the working muscle, while heart and lung function improves. Many small capillary blood vessels appear in the working muscle.

Thus, the nutritional conditions for muscle development are improved, and general blood circulation is eased. During the student period, blood circulation is slower than that of a young child. In order to accelerate blood circulation, it is necessary to activate the work of the heart. Heart activity, in turn, improves due to muscle work. When the muscles contract, blood moves through the veins to the heart, and when the muscles relax, it flows from the capillaries to the veins.

Restlessness, inactivity, lack of sufficient movements have a negative effect on the heart and cause various diseases.

The analysis of literary sources and conducted researches confirms that in the physical education practical training, the educational load is used for the formation of movement skills and management of movements according to the curriculum. The results are not visible, because the volume and intensity of the training load is not very high. Physical education methods and tools do not take into account the typological characteristics of the person, physical development, physical condition, and the characteristics of the Central Asian climate. From the above, it can be concluded that there are almost no scientifically based physical exercises aimed at reaching physical maturity of young people, preserving and strengthening health, and increasing work ability. Therefore, the method of mathematical statistics is used to determine scientifically based physical exercises. A special program has been developed to determine the features of interdependence of pedagogical process

factors. The factors included in the pedagogical process are interrelated. The ability to change one factor in accordance with the change of another factor increases the effectiveness of the pedagogical process.

It is known that in the process of training physical qualities, there is a positive relationship between the development of strength, speed, and endurance in some cases, and sometimes there is no correlation, that is, the qualities listed above

if it develops, other qualities will also develop, and finally, negative correlation, that is, if one quality develops, it will have a bad effect on the development of other qualities. Research in the field of physical education is primarily related to the study of the process of educational rehabilitation. Pedagogical effect in the form of the development of movement qualities, characteristics of the functions of the heart-blood system testifies to the advantages of the used tips and tools. Pedagogical effect is characterized in two ways (qualitative and quantitative).

Methodology enriches pedagogy with statistical methods of research. They make it possible to express the objective laws they have discovered in the form of a mathematical model, that is, in the form of one or another relationship between indicators characterizing various aspects of the studied phenomenon. Such a model of certain relationships between indicators is called functional dependence. Its essence is that a change in one indicator, as a rule, leads to a corresponding change in the second indicator. Knowledge of functional dependence allows predicting the parameters of the dependent quantity (function) depending on any parameters of the controlling quantity (argument). From this comes the functional practical and scientific significance. Functional models provide an opportunity to predict the course of the described process, control this process and help to choose effective pedagogical methods.

A functional relationship reflects a strict dependence, in which a change in the value of one factor causes a similar change in the value of the second factor. Such

communication is characteristic for exact sciences. In pedagogy, they are observed in general options and conditional limits.

It is desirable to establish statistical relationships or correlations. Correlation makes it possible to find statistically accurate numerical dimensions of dependence in the case where not one, but several values of another factor correspond to one factor. In this case, the relationship is expressed in the average values of a series of changes obtained. There are several directions of correlation: right positive, negative; inverse positive, negative correlations.

Numerical indicators of communication are divided into several levels: weak communication - correlation coefficient up to 0.30; average correlation-coefficient from 0.31 to 0.69; a strong correlation-coefficient of 0.70 to 0.99.

Correlation dependence of physical development, body structure, physical and functional readiness indicators is defined in order to determine the effective means of improving the health of students. Researches on the assessment of the quality of movement, physical development, body structure, and the level of physical condition indicators were conducted on 36 tests for girls and 47 tests for boys.

Such an approach, i.e., identification of scientifically based exercises for physical training of students, allows effective planning of health-preventive work, selection of tools in accordance with the goal of accelerating the health process.

It is known that there is a significant correlation between height and weight ($r=0.9$), lung capacity and neck circumference, wrist dynamometry and body fat weight in girls. In boys, there is a significant correlation between height and weight, wrist dynamometry and body strength ($r=0.9$).

A functional dependence has been identified between body structure and physical development of boys and girls, which make up a small number of connections. Body structure, improvement of physical development is one of the main conditions of physical education of students, it is achieved through regular use

of special exercises aimed at developing strength in the process of health. The development of the body structure allows to improve the figure, which ensures the normal functioning of the spine.

Correlational dependence of indicators of student's typological characteristics revealed a rather large ($r=0.6$) dependence between arousal and activity of nervous processes.

Students with a high power of awakening and mobility of nervous processes will have good physical fitness. Physical exercises with high movement activity and frequent changes in posture are recommended for them. Exercises that require the same speed are suitable for students with low excitation and motility of nervous processes and high braking power. Exercises involving a large number of muscles, with high movement activity, help to improve the functioning of the heart and blood system.

Identified dependencies make it possible to define scientifically based requirements that are taken into account in the selection of physical exercises used in the process of valeological education of students. This ensures the effectiveness of the educational process.

The results obtained from the research on the characteristics of blood circulation in students of different ages and genders revealed a high correlation ($r=0.9$) between the constant index of blood circulation and the index of blood circulation, while the increase in blood circulation improves blood circulation and metabolism. Meanwhile, there is a high negative correlation ($r=0.9$) between the blood circulation index and peripheral vascular resistance. Movement activity increases the contractile and pumping function of muscles, which ensures venous blood flow to the heart, reduces the peripheral resistance of the vessels, and increases the efficiency of the heart-blood system. The mentioned factors should be taken into account when choosing the tools used in the lessons of valeological education of students.

Thus, a certain morphofunctional state of the muscle system is an important vital necessity, and its level is reflected in the indicators of muscle strength. It follows that a certain level of muscular system is necessary for health. In practical training, increasing movement activity, including upper shoulder girth, abdominal press muscle strengthening agents in physical exercises, increasing their tone, improving stature, preventing stature disorders improves the functioning of moving and internal organs.

Taking into account the above, it can be concluded that all-round preparation requires improvement of human physical abilities and is an important factor of harmonic development achieved through special exercises.

CONCLUSION

The healing forces of nature as an effective means of improving health.

Solar radiation, characteristics of air and water environments serve as means of strengthening the student's health, training and improving work ability.

In the course of valeological education, within the framework of natural research, the healing forces of nature were used in two directions:

1. Use as an additional condition in physical education training (training in the open air), where the natural factors of the environment complement, strengthen and activate the effect of physical training;
2. Organization of remedial swimming classes in an open water pool (swimming pool), where natural factors are dosed as relatively independent means of exercise and health.

Health swimming is held in April and October. According to the information of the Hydrometeorological Center of the Republic of Uzbekistan, this is the most convenient time of the year for healthy swimming.

The health-giving forces of nature and hygienic factors helped to improve the health of students and increase the effectiveness of educational activities as valeological education tools.

According to the conclusion of our research, physical exercises in the environment of natural factors increase the resistance of the body to the effects of the external environment.

Outdoor practical training in the stadium 1.09. from 30.11. to and 1.03. from 1.06. to 1.06. will be held in conditions of air temperature from +10 to +28. It is important to note that when the air temperature exceeds +27, students perform physical exercises sometimes in the sun, sometimes in the cool. Various methods were used in the outdoor research. These are: strictly regulated exercises, methods of games and competitions, influence through speech and exhibition, and hz. As a result of testing combinations of different methods, an effective combination of game and competition method was determined. In the course of competitions, the competitive factor (pulling on the beams, standing on the floor, bending the hands and writing), as well as the conditions of their organization and conduct (incentives for the achieved result) create a special mental mood. Determining the student's rating enhances the effect of physical exercises and helps to maximize the functional capabilities of the body. The results of the above studies show that physical fitness in competitive conditions is much more advanced than in other non-competition methods.

In the process of pedagogical research, the factors determining the effect of physical exercises were determined.

1. Personal characteristics of teachers and students are an important factor. Teaching is a two-way process. The effect of physical exercises depends on the moral qualities, knowledge level, skills, physical development, interest and activity of the persons teaching and learning.
2. Scientific factors characterize the measures of studying the laws of valeological education on the part of the student. The more thoroughly the pedagogical, psychological and physiological aspects of physical exercises are developed, the more effectively they can be used to solve pedagogical issues.

3. Methodological methods include a group of requirements for physical exercises. The effectiveness of teaching depends on how well the selected exercises match the capabilities of the student. Individualized training means choosing physical exercises according to personal characteristics. This requires medical, psychological and pedagogical knowledge from the student. Knowing the personal characteristics of students is the basis of pedagogical cooperation "pedagogue-student-pedagogue". At the same time, identifying the personal characteristics of students activates the effect of physical training.

Individualization of the process of physical development is expressed by the differentiation of trainings, the ways of their passage, the standards of physical load and the ways of their management, the types of training and the methods of pedagogical influence.

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